

What are key factors for detection of peptides using mass spectrometry on boron-doped diamond surfaces?

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Abstract

Here, we investigated the use of boron-doped diamond (BDD) with different surface morphologies for the enhanced detection of nine different peptides by matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionisation mass spectrometry (MALDI-MS). For the first time, we compared three different nanostructured BDD film morphologies (continuous, nanograss, and nanotips) with differently terminated surfaces (-H, -O, and -F) to the commercially available ground steel plate. All these surfaces were evaluated for their effectiveness in detecting the nine different peptides by MALDI-MS. Our results demonstrated that certain nanostructured BDD surfaces exhibited superior performance for the detection of especially hydrophobic peptides (*i.e.* bradykinin 1-7, substance P and renin substrate) with a limit of detection down as low as 2.3 pM. Further investigation showed that hydrophobic peptides (*i.e.* bradykinin 1-7, substance P and renin substrate) were effectively detected on hydrogen-terminated BDD surfaces with positive electronegativity potential drop ($C^{\delta-}-H^{\delta+}$) and negative electron affinity (NEA). On the other hand, highly acidic negatively charged peptide adrenocorticotrophic hormone fragment 18-39 was effectively identified on oxygen-/fluorine-terminated BDD surfaces with negative electronegativity drop ($C^{\delta+}-O(-F)^{\delta-}$) and positive electron affinity (PEA).

Graphical abstract

Keywords: boron-doped diamond, surface termination, peptides, MALDI, mass spectrometry, nanostructures

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40 1. Introduction

41 Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization mass spectrometry (MALDI-MS) is an effective tool for the
42 analysis of (bio)molecules of interest under the desorption/ionization process to produce positively charged
43 single ions [1]. MALDI-MS is extensively used for the analysis of medically relevant biomolecules such as
44 proteins, post-translational modifications of proteins, and peptides [2, 3]. Peptides have important functions in
45 cellular communication, and they can be used as candidates for biomarker discovery and precise disease
46 diagnosis [4]. Currently, one of the most studied techniques for small biomolecules detection are based on
47 the application of nanostructured surfaces [5]. Recently novel nanostructured steel plates possessing a large
48 surface, laser absorption efficiency, and high ionization efficiency were used for the analysis of small and
49 large molecules [1].

50 A porous silicon layer was successfully used as a support, resulting in the detection levels of analyte as
51 low as femtomole (or attomole) with little or no analyte fragmentation [6]. Similarly, a highly porous activated
52 carbon layer deposited on an alumina support was shown as a viable alternative solution to silicon layers [7].
53 The recorded mass spectra were almost clean with only a few background ion peaks appearing at low mass.
54 Both these results and the rapid progress in nanomaterial synthesis boosted researchers to test a variety of
55 nanomaterials, such as metal nanoparticles (Au, Ag), metal oxides (ZnO, Fe₃O₄), metal-organic frameworks,
56 or sp²-hybridized carbon nano-forms [8-15].

57 Diamond, the sp³-hybridized carbon, possesses an extraordinary combination of intrinsic properties
58 including high hardness, excellent thermal conductivity, chemical inertness to harsh conditions, and tuneable
59 surface chemistry (*i.e.* the ability to tailor the surface charge and electron affinity) [16]. Moreover, its electrical
60 properties can be tuned from an insulating to semi-metallic material through doping with boron [17, 18]. The
61 surface morphology of diamond can be technologically controlled, ranging from micro- to nano-scale
62 structural features. The deep nanoporous etches can be easily made by reactive ion etching [19, 20] or a
63 novel process called molten salt thermal etching [21]. Additionally, its surface wettability can be varied
64 through atomic termination with elements such as oxygen, hydrogen, fluorine, or amine [22]. In this view, the
65 diamond appears as a promising platform for MALDI-MS, which has not been yet explored.

66 In this article, we provide application of the BDD interface in the bioanalysis since BDD can be deposited
67 with an excellent uniformity [23]. BDD was applied for MALDI-MS analysis with a focus on the assay of
68 peptides for the first time.

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70 2. Experimental part

71 2.1. Chemicals

72 MALDI matrix 2,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid (DHB) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany),
73 trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) from Fisher Scientific (UK), acetonitrile (ACN) from Merck KGaA (Germany) were
74 purchased from Honeywell (Germany). The nine peptides used as standards for MS were purchased from
75 Sigma-Aldrich (Germany). Peptides bradykinin 1-7 (*Brad*), angiotensin II (*Ang II*), angiotensin I (*Ang I*),
76 bombesin (*Bomb*), renin substrate (*Ren S*), adrenocorticotrophic hormone fragment 1-17 (ACTH 1-17;
77 *AC1*), adrenocorticotrophic hormone fragment 18-39 (ACTH 18-39; *AC18*) and somatostatin (*Som*) were
78 provided from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany) and substance P (*Sub P*) from Hello bio (Ireland). The peptides were
79 selected based on the preliminary experiment with Bruker's peptide standard (consisting of all peptides
80 described above).

81

82 2.2. Diamond growth and structuring

83 Boron-doped diamond (BDD) films were grown on polished Si (100) and Al₂O₃ substrates, cleaned in
84 acetone, isopropyl alcohol, and DI (deionized) water, and ultrasonically seeded with diamond nanoparticles (5
85 nm) in DI water suspension (50 mg l⁻¹). Depositions were carried out in the linear antenna microwave (MW)
86 plasma chemical vapour deposition (CVD) reactor (Cube 300, scia Ltd., Germany) using 6 kW of microwave
87 power in a pulse (2 × 3 kW with power on and off set at 8 and 6 ms, respectively, and 50% phase change for
88 each of the two antennas), for 30 h at the substrate temperature of 590 °C. A gas mixture consisting of
89 hydrogen, evaporated trimethyl borate (TMBT, 1%) and carbon dioxide (0.2%) with a pressure of 30 Pa was

90 used to maintain the growth of the diamond layer using a gas phase with $C_{B/C} = 312500$ ppm (resistivity of
91 $0.017 \Omega \text{ cm}$, $n = 2.9 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ according to Hall measurements) [24].

92 Nanograss and nanotip morphologies were formed on the surface of BDD layers using dry etching in
93 radiofrequency (RF) plasma (PE-200, Plasma etch, USA) employing the self-masking nanostructuring
94 process previously described in [19]. Nanograss morphology was formed by etching for 60 min in O_2 plasma
95 (3 Pa, 200 W), and nanotips were etched by a 30 min etching process in H_2/N_2 plasma (6 Pa, 500 W). All
96 samples were washed in a solution of NH_4 , H_2O_2 and demineralized water (1:1:4) for 10 min at 80°C to
97 remove amorphous carbon from the surface.

98 One-third of the samples were hydrogenated in a linear antenna MW plasma CVD system in pure
99 hydrogen plasma for 60 minutes under the following conditions: microwave power of $2 \times 1.7 \text{ kW}$; substrate
100 temperature of about 330°C ; and total gas pressure of 15 Pa. The second third of the samples was
101 fluorinated in capacitively-coupled plasma reactive ion etching (CCP-RIE) Phantom System (Trion
102 Technology, US) at discharge power of 100 W, exposure time of 30 s, pressure of 20 Pa, and CF_4 flow of 20
103 $\text{cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The last third of the samples were oxidized in RF plasma for 1 min at 6 Pa and 200 W (PE-200,
104 Plasma etch, USA).

105

106 **2.3. Substrate preparation for MALDI-MS analysis**

107 The BDD/ Al_2O_3 substrates were selectively passivated by a silicone-based screen-printing paste with
108 mineral filler 240-SB (FERRO, Mayfield Heights, OH, USA) using a semi-automatic printing machine (TY-
109 600H, ATMA, Taoyuan City, Taiwan) and contacted with Ag paste AST6025 (SunChemical, Parsippany, NJ,
110 USA) and Cu wiring to create the reusable target plate for MALDI-MS analyses.

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112 **2.4. Scanning electron microscopy**

113 The surface morphology of the fabricated diamond films/structures was analysed using a field-emission
114 scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) operating in secondary electron mode (MAIA3, Tescan Ltd.,
115 Czechia) using a beam energy of 10 keV.

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117 **2.5. Raman spectroscopy**

118 Raman spectra of the prepared samples were acquired by Renishaw InVia Reflex Raman spectrometer
119 (UK) equipped with He-Cd laser with an excitation wavelength of 442 nm and an air-cooled CCD detector.
120 For the measurements, we used a Leica with $100\times$ magnification ($NA = 0.9$) and the total laser power at the
121 total exposure on the sample of 8.25 mW. The accumulation time was set to 30 s for all measurements.
122 Before the measurements, the Raman spectrometer was calibrated on the crystalline diamond peak (1332
123 cm^{-1}).

124

125 **2.6. Contact angle measurements**

126 The wetting properties of the as-grown and surface-terminated (H-, O-, F-) diamond film surfaces were
127 determined by contact angle measurements at room temperature by using a static method in a material-water
128 droplet system. A water droplet of $3 \mu\text{L}$ in volume was dropped onto the investigated diamond surface and
129 the formed drop was captured by a digital charged-couple device camera. The contact angle, used to assess
130 the wetting properties of the surface, was calculated by using the Surface Energy Evaluation (SEE) System
131 (Masaryk University, Czechia) for the multipoint fitting of the drop profile.

132

133 **2.7. Photoelectron spectroscopy**

134 The X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) spectra and ultraviolet photoelectron spectroscopy (UPS)
135 spectra were obtained using an AXIS-Supra photoelectron spectrometer (Japan) equipped with
136 monochromatised Al $K\alpha$ radiation (1486.7 eV) and He I light source (21.2 eV). The measurements were
137 carried out with a photoelectron emission angle of 90° , X-ray power of 150 W, energy step of 0.1 eV, and
138 pass energy of 10 eV, ensuring an overall energy resolution of 0.45 eV for high-resolution core level spectra.

139 To quantify atomic composition, integrated high-resolution core level peak areas were analysed after
 140 Shirley's electron inelastic background subtraction. This analysis was performed with the ESCAPE software
 141 (Kratos Analytical Ltd.), which incorporates atomic sensitivity factors. The UPS spectra were measured with a
 142 55 μm aperture and bias of 9 V (spectra were calibrated to compensate the applied bias).

143

144 2.8. Sample preparation

145 DHB matrix solution was prepared as 20 mg mL⁻¹ in TA30 (30% ACN/70% H₂O/0.1% TFA). Peptide stock
 146 solutions were prepared at 1 mg mL⁻¹ in TA30 and then diluted to a final concentration of 100nM, 10nM and
 147 1nM with TA30 for each peptide. The details about peptides used in the study are provided in **Tab. 1** and
 148 **Tab. S1**. For analysis of peptides via MALDI-MS, 1 μL of samples were spotted on Ground Steel 800/384 TF
 149 MALDI target (Bruker Daltonics, MA, USA) or continuous BDD, BDD nanograss, and BDD nanotips surfaces
 150 and mixed with 1 μL of DHB matrix solution, the spots were dried at lab temperature.

151

152 **Table 1.** Characteristics of the peptides used in the study

Peptide N°	Sequence	Mass (Da)*	[M+H] ⁺	[M+Na] ⁺	pI [#]	Charge pH 7.4 [#]
Bradykinin 1-7 (<i>Brad</i>)	RPPGFSP	757.4	758.4	780.4	9.1	+0.19
Angiotensin II (<i>Ang II</i>)	DRVYIHPF	1046.5	1047.5	1069.5	6.9	-0.29
Angiotensin I (<i>Ang I</i>)	DRVYIHPFHL	1296.7	1297.7	1319.7	7.1	-0.25
Substance P (<i>Sub P</i>)	RPKPQQFFGLM	1347.7	1348.7	1370.7	10.7	+1.18
Bombesin (<i>Bomb</i>) [¶]	OQRLGNQWAVGHLM	1619.8	1620.8	1642.8	11.1	+1.04
Renin Subst. (<i>Ren S</i>)	DRVYIHPFHLVIHN	1758.9	1759.9	1781.9	7.2	-0.20
ACTH 1-17 (<i>AC1</i>)	SYSMEHFRWGKPVGKKR	2093.1	2094.1	2116.1	10.3	+3.26
ACTH 18-39 (<i>AC18</i>)	RPVKVYPNGAEDESAEAFPLEF	2465.2	2466.2	2488.2	4.3	-3.82
Somatostatin	SANSPAMAPRERKAGCKNFFWKTFTSC	3147.5	3148.5	3170.5	9.6	+3.07

153 *Monoisotopic mass (Da); [#] pI and charge quantification was done using an on-line tool [25]; [¶] pI and charge quantification
 154 for bombesin was done for the sequence: QRLGNQWAVGHLM since Pyr (pyroglutamic acid) could not be inserted into
 155 an on-line tool for quantification of pI (isoelectric point) and a charge of the full composition of bombesin. O = Pyr
 156 (pyroglutamic acid).

157 3D structure of the peptides (**Fig. S1**) was generated from a PDB file, which was computed by the on-line
 158 tool I-TASSER through the web page of Yang Zhang's research group [26-29]. The 3D images of peptides
 159 were visualised using Deep View/Swiss-PdbViewer software showing the peptide backbone and the surface
 160 of the peptide using electrostatic potential values. *Brad* and *Ang II* are too short peptides for which generation
 161 of a pdb file was not possible.

162

163 2.9. MALDI-MS analysis

164 The samples were analysed by an UltrafleXtreme II Mass Spectrometer (Bruker Daltonics, MA, USA). The
 165 spectra were acquired in reflectron positive ion mode collecting 6000 shots for all the measurements, the
 166 laser was operated at 337 nm wavelength. A mass window of m/z 500–3500 was selected for the analysis of
 167 the peptides. The data was acquired with FlexControl 3.4 and processed with FlexAnalysis 3.4 software
 168 program (both Bruker Daltonics, MA, USA). LOD for the peptides were calculated as S/N=3.

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3. Results and Discussion

3.1. SEM analysis of BDD

178 **Fig. 1** shows representative SEM images of as-grown (continuous) and structured (nanograss and
179 nanotips) BDD films. The continuous film (the first row in **Fig. 1**) reveals the typical nanocrystalline character
180 of a diamond film with grain size in the range from about 20 to 200 nm. The diamond film thickness is about
181 4.6 μm with a quite smooth surface. After the structuring processes, nanograss- and nanotips-like surface
182 features (the second and the third row in **Fig. 1**, respectively) were fabricated. In the case of nanograss
183 structure, approximately 300-nm thick top-layer has been converted into a dense “forest” of sharp diamond
184 peaks also cleaned from graphitic phases (see **Fig. 1**, 2nd row-nanograss-angle view 45°). The overall
185 thickness of the film remained the same. The nanotips structure has not revealed such deep and sharp
186 structures on the top as the nanograss sample. Moreover, the total film thickness decreased to 3.5 μm due to
187 different structuring process parameters.

Figure 1: SEM images (top, angle, and cross-section views) of BDD morphologies for continuous film, and structured into nanograss or nanotips.

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3.2. Raman analysis of BDD

190 It is important to note, that structuring processes have a negligible effect on the bulk chemical composition
191 of the BDD films as confirmed by the Raman measurements in **Fig. 2**. The Raman spectra of all three kinds
192 of samples reveal the same features with the characteristic Fano-shaped highly boron-doped diamond bands
193 around 460 cm^{-1} (B_1) and 1200 cm^{-1} (B_2). The zone-centre phonon mode of cubic diamond at 1290 cm^{-1}
194 (ZCP_D) is red shifted from its original position in intrinsic diamond at 1332.9 cm^{-1} due to the 'Fano' effect and
195 phonon confinement caused by incorporated boron atoms [30]. The band at around 1530 cm^{-1} (G-band) is
196 attributed to the graphitic sp^2 hybridized carbon phases.

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200 3.3. Contact angle measurements of BDD

201 The water contact angle (CA) measurements are shown in **Fig. 3** and illustratively present the effect of the
202 diamond surface termination at different conditions. The as-grown continuous BDD diamond films reveal
203 hydrophobic properties with a contact angle of about 69°. After the structuring process (here nanotips
204 fabrication) the CA decreased to about 10°. Further, plasma-based oxidisation of the diamond surface
205 revealed unambiguously hydrophilic properties with a contact angle value lower than 4°. After hydrogen
206 plasma treatment, the diamond film exhibited strong hydrophobic properties (contact angle of about 90°).
207 Finally, after the fluorination process, the diamond film exhibited super-hydrophobic properties (contact angle
208 more than 120°). Within the different sets of structures (continuous, nanograss and nanotips) some
209 differences in the value of CA were observed due to an additional effect of the diamond film surface
210 roughness, however, the trends remain the same.

Figure 2: Raman spectra of the as-grown (continuous) and structured (nanograss and nanotips) BDD films.

Figure 3: Wetting properties of as-grown (continuous) and structured (nanotips) BDD samples after different surface termination treatments.

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212 3.4. XPS measurements of BDD

213 The atomic composition of the BDD sample surfaces (before peptide absorption) was derived by XPS
 214 measurements. The composition is outlined in **Table 2**. The representative XPS survey spectra are shown in
 215 **Fig. 4**. The presence of p-type Boron dopant in nanocrystalline diamond substrates with concentrations
 216 ranging from 1 at.% to 3 at.% (10000 – 30000 ppm) was confirmed in both as-grown continuous and
 217 structured samples with different surface terminations. XPS identified various bonding types of Boron,
 218 including B-C and B-O bonds on the samples' surfaces (not shown here). Consequently, B atoms could be
 219 present as a dopant within the nanocrystalline diamond grains as well as an adsorbant on the diamond
 220 surface. The concentrations of O (8.3 at.%) and N (1.1 at.%) on the surface were relatively high in the as-
 221 grown continuous samples and increased further after the structuring process, particularly for Nanograss and
 222 Nanotips samples. The appearance of Si and Al contaminants is attributed to signals originating from the
 223 substrate beneath the nanocrystalline diamond layers.

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225 **Table 2:** Composition of the Continuous, Nanograss, and Nanotips samples with as-grown, -H, -F, and -O termination
 226 derived from XPS measurements.

Sample	Atomic concentration, at.%						
	C	O	B	F	N	Si	Al
Continuous	88.1	8.3	2.1	0.0	1.1	0.4	0.0
Nanograss	77.0	18.9	1.9	0.0	1.7	0.5	0.0
Nanotips	81.0	11.8	2.1	0.0	5.1	0.0	0.0
Continuous-H	94.2	3.0	1.8	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0
Nanograss-H	64.1	21.9	1.0	0.0	0.0	13.0	0.0
Nanotips-H	89.2	6.4	1.2	0.0	0.0	3.2	0.0
Continuous-F	75.6	2.8	2.3	17.5	0.9	0.0	0.9
Nanograss-F	66.2	6.2	2.0	24.0	0.8	0.0	0.8

Nanotips-F	65.8	3.2	1.8	27.8	0.7	0.0	0.7
Continuous-O	85.9	9.0	3.0	1.6	0.5	0.0	0.0
Nanograss-O	75.6	20.4	2.4	0.7	0.9	0.0	0.0
Nanotips-O	75.5	17.4	2.4	2.5	2.2	0.0	0.0

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228 Following H and F plasma treatments, the concentration of O and N contaminants decreased. However,
 229 these treatments, along with the etching of continuous film and surface plasma treatment, led to an increase
 230 in sample surface roughness and potential variation in BDD film thickness on the sample surface.
 231 Consequently, the concentrations of (Si and Al increased on -H and -F terminated surfaces, respectively. It's
 232 noteworthy that the high concentration of O (21.9 at.%) on the Nanograss-H sample is associated with an
 233 increase in Si concentration (13.0 at.%) on the surface.

234 In O-terminated samples, a high oxygen concentration was measured on sample surfaces (note, with a
 235 lower concentration of silicon and aluminium atoms from the substrate). Oxygen concentrations were higher
 236 for structured Nanograss-O (20.4 at.%) and Nanotips-O (17.4 at.%) samples, with enhanced sample surface
 237 areas, compared to the continuous BDD-O (9.0 at.%) sample. A similar trend was observed for F-terminated
 238 samples, where the F concentration was higher for Nanograss-F (24 at.%) and Nanotips-F (27.8 at.%)
 239 samples than for the continuous BDD-F sample (17.5 at.%).

Figure 4: XPS survey spectra of (a) Continuous BDD, (b) Nanograss BDD, and (c) Nanotips BDD samples with as-prepared (black), -H (red), -O (green), and -F (blue) terminations.

240 **Table 3:** Results of UPS measurements for Continuous, Nanograss, and Nanotips BDD substrates with as-grown, -H, -O,
 241 and -F terminations. Energy edges of valence band maxima (E_{VBM}), cutoff energies (E_{cutoff}), conduction band minima
 242 (E_{CBM}), diamond's band gap (E_{BG}), derived values of work functions (WF), and electron affinities (EA) are provided in eV.
 243 The negative electron affinity (NEA) was observed on the H-terminated BDD samples.

Sample	Energy, eV				WF, eV	EA, eV
	E_{VBM}	E_{cutoff}	E_{CBM}	E_{BG}		
Continuous	2.3	17.0	-3.2	5.5	4.2	1.0
Nanograss	1.5	16.3	-4.0	5.5	4.9	0.9
Nanotips	1.9	16.8	-3.6	5.5	4.4	0.8
						NEA
Continuous-H	0.7	17.1	-4.8	5.5	4.1	-0.7
Nanograss-H	1.2	17.2	-4.3	5.5	4.0	-0.3
Nanotips-H	1.1	17.3	-4.4	5.5	3.9	-0.5
Continuous-F	1.0	15.7	-4.5	5.5	5.5	1.0
Nanograss-F	1.1	15.4	-4.4	5.5	5.8	1.4
Nanotips-F	1.7	15.6	-3.8	5.5	5.6	1.8
Continuous-O	1.2	16.1	-4.3	5.5	5.1	0.8
Nanograss-O	1.8	15.9	-3.7	5.5	5.3	1.6
Nanotips-O	1.9	15.9	-3.6	5.5	5.3	1.7

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245 3.5. UPS measurements of BDD

246 Distinct surface terminations led to surface dipole charge variations on the BDD sample surface, *i.e.*, also
 247 reflected in a change in surface zeta potential or electron affinity [31]. Specifically, negative electron affinity
 248 (NEA) or positive electron affinity (PEA) is observed on H-terminated or on O- and F-terminated diamond
 249 surfaces, respectively. UPS measurements of BDD samples confirmed NEA for H-terminated samples only
 250 independently on surface structuring (see **Tab. 3** and **Fig. S2**).

251 The valence band maxima (VBM) and the energy cutoffs were determined by extrapolating the UPS
 252 spectra edges to the zero intensity levels. The electron affinity (EA) was computed as follows:

$$253 \text{ EA} = \text{WF} - E_{V-M} - E_{BG},$$

254 where the work function ($\text{WF} = 21.2 - E_{cutoff}$) was computed from the cutoff energy of valence band spectra
 255 and excitation light energy, E_{VBM} is the extrapolated edge of the valence band maxima, and E_{BG} is a band gap
 256 of diamond. Measured and computed values are included in **Tab. 3**. The negative EA was derived for H-
 257 terminated samples, whereas positive EA was derived for as-grown continuous, -F, and -O terminated
 258 samples.

259 These findings are in good agreement with the expected impact of the surface dipole formed on the
 260 diamond band alignment. When the diamond surface is terminated with non-diamond elements, in our case
 261 hydrogen, oxygen or fluorine, the charge dipole is formed due to differences in electronegativity values (δ) of
 262 these elements (carbon 2.55, hydrogen 2.2, oxygen 3.44, and fluorine 3.98). In the case of the H-terminated
 263 diamond surface, different values of δ result in a positive potential drop ($\text{C}^{\delta-} - \text{H}^{\delta+}$) along the C-H bond that
 264 pushes the surface vacuum level down, ultimately leading to a negative electron affinity in our case ranging
 265 from -0.3 to -0.5 eV. It should be noted that this value should be as high as -1.3 eV for C(111) single crystal
 266 diamond [32]. For the O-/F-terminations, the opposite dipole ($\text{C}^{\delta+} - \text{X}^{\delta-}$) is formed and characteristic values of
 267 EA are positive. The continuous BDD/H samples revealed also positive values of EA, which should be
 268 attributed to the washing procedure used to remove the amorphous carbon from the surface.

269

270 3.6. MALDI-MS analysis of peptides

271 ;For MALDI-MS measurements, 0.5 μL of the peptide mixture (**Tab. 1**) with a concentration of 0.2 $\text{pmol } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$
272 was spotted on the BDD surfaces (**Fig. 5**) or ground steel MALDI chip surface, mixed with matrix and dried at
273 room temperature, and measured by MALDI-TOF. The MALDI-MS workflow together with representative
274 spectra for a mixture of all peptides is shown in **Fig. 6**. Further characteristics of peptides (*i.e.* percentage of
275 class of amino acids present within peptides) are shown in **Tab. S1** and a graphical representation in **Fig. 7**.
276 In **Fig. 7** there is also depicted an average percentage of hydrophobic amino acids present in *Brad*, *Sub P*
277 and *Ren S* as a dashed line (average value for *Brad*, *Sub P* and *Ren S* peptides).

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280 **Figure 5:** Photography of prepared MALDI-MS chip with BDD spots deposited.

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284 **Figure 6:** MALDI-MS workflow and MS spectra of the standard peptide mixture solution (0.2 pmol μL^{-1}) performed in
 285 positive mode using DHB matrix in all cases (A) Ground Steel and (B) Continuous BDD (C) Nanograss BDD.

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288 **Figure 7:** Class of amino acids present in the peptides expressed in %. **Brad:** Bradykinin 1-7; **Ang II:** Angiotensin II; **Ang**
 289 **I:** Angiotensin I; **Sub P:** Substance P; **Bomb:** Bombesin; **Ren S:** Renin Subst.; **AC 1:** adrenocorticotrophic hormone
 290 fragment 1-17; **AC 18:** adrenocorticotrophic hormone fragment 18-39; **Som:** Somatostatin. Peptides highlighted in
 291 green showed significantly better LOD when detected on BDD interfaces in comparison to the commercially available
 292 ground steel chip. The figure was made based on data taken from **Tab. S1**. The dashed green line represents the
 293 average percentage of hydrophobic amino acids present in **Brad**, **Sub P** and **Ren S**.

294

295 Individual peptides (**Tab. 1** and **Tab. S1**) from small to large sizes with m/z from 700 to 3200 were
 296 measured by MALDI-MS to investigate the efficiency of their detection by MALDI-MS. **Ang II** is a peptide that
 297 plays a key role in balancing the renin-angiotensin system [33], a dysregulation can cause cardiovascular
 298 diseases [34]. **Ang I** and **Ren S** both can be used as potential molecular biomarkers for the treatment and
 299 diagnosis of cardiovascular diseases [35, 36]. The nanostructured BDD nanotips surface terminated by -H,
 300 reached the limit of detection (LOD) of 12.2 pM for **Ang II** with m/z of 1047 (**Tab. 4**). Moreover, **Ang I** with m/z
 301 of 1296 was detected on BDD nanotips surface terminated by -H reaching LOD of 16 pM (**Tab. 4**). **Ren S** with
 302 1759 reached LOD of 3.1 pM using BDD nanogross modified interface terminated by -H (**Tab. 4**).

303

304 **Table 4:** The results from MALDI-MS analysis of peptides on differently terminated and structured BDD surfaces,
 305 including ground steel chip.

Peptide	Surface/ termination	Continuous BDD		Nanogross BDD		Nanotips BDD	
		LOD (pM)	LOD _{ratio} *	LOD (pM)	LOD _{ratio} *	LOD (pM)	LOD _{ratio} *
Sub P	BDD/H	6.2	7.03	43.7	1.00	8.1	5.42
	BDD/O	2.3	19.19	18.7	2.34	51.0	0.86
	BDD/F	56.1	0.78	63.9	0.68	31.0	1.41
	Steel chip	43.8					
Ang II	BDD/H	27.3	1.24	33.6	1.01	12.2	2.78
	BDD/O	29.1	1.17	57.6	0.59	316.3	0.11
	BDD/F	422.0	0.08	31.5	1.08	51.3	0.66
	Steel chip	34.0					
AC 1	BDD/H	19.4	2.78	42.7	1.27	54.5	0.99
	BDD/O	ND	ND	63.9	0.85	63.9	0.85
	BDD/F	63.9	0.85	63.9	0.85	63.9	0.85
	Steel chip	54.1					
AC 18	BDD/H	54.1	1.64	51.7	1.72	54.3	1.64
	BDD/O	21.1	4.21	63.9	1.39	63.9	1.39

	BDD/F	63.9	1.39	63.9	1.39	63.9	1.39
	Steel chip	88.9					
Ang I	BDD/H	141.4	0.22	47.6	0.66	16.0	1.95
	BDD/O	84.8	0.37	63.9	0.49	33.2	0.94
	BDD/F	49.9	0.63	63.9	0.49	37.6	0.83
	Steel chip	31.2					
Bomb	BDD/H	31.8	1.87	266.6	0.22	35.6	1.67
	BDD/O	40.4	1.48	753.8	0.08	40.4	1.48
	BDD/F	63.9	0.93	63.9	0.93	63.9	0.93
	Steel chip	59.6					
Brad	BDD/H	51.9	1.73	63.9	1.41	723.8	0.12
	BDD/O	18.9	4.76	63.9	1.41	25.8	3.49
	BDD/F	15.2	5.92	247.2	0.36	63.9	1.41
	Steel chip	90.0					
Ren S	BDD/H	21.6	2.14	3.1	14.94	51.1	0.91
	BDD/O	54.9	0.84	63.9	0.72	16.8	2.76
	BDD/F	63.9	0.72	63.9	0.72	63.9	0.72
	Steel chip	46.3					
Som	BDD/H	63.9	1.00	63.9	1.00	63.9	1.00
	BDD/O	ND	ND	63.9	1.00	ND	ND
	BDD/F	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
	Steel chip	63.9					

306 * $LOD_{ratio} = LOD_{steel} / LOD_{BDD}$ (LOD_{steel} is the limit of detection achieved on ground steel and LOD_{BDD} is limit of detection
307 achieved on BDD surfaces). The higher the LOD_{ratio} , the better performance of peptide analysis by MALDI-MS on BDD
308 interfaces in comparison to commercially available ground steel chip. LOD values lower than 10 pM are shown in **black**
309 **bold**, while LOD ratio values higher than 5 are shown in **red bold**.

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Figure 8: 3D plots showing the dependence of LOD_{ratio} on m/z and charge.

318 When considering other peptides, especially *Sub P* with m/z 1348 could be detected with very low LOD on
319 several interfaces *i.e.* 6.2 pM (continuous BDD terminated by -H); 2.3 pM (continuous BDD terminated by -O)
320 and 8.1 pM (BDD nanotips terminated by -H) (**Tab. 4**). *Sub P* is a neuropeptide which acts as a
321 neuromodulator, its increased levels are correlated to Parkinson's disease. Thus, it is considered a promising
322 biomarker for Parkinson's disease [37]. LOD for all combinations of peptides and BDD interfaces together
323 with ground steel are summarised in **Tab. 4**. This study demonstrated low background signals, high
324 sensitivity and very low LOD values. In recent studies reported in the literature, Cournot *et al.* [1] used
325 MALDI-MS and SALDI-MS to investigate the desorption/ionisation efficiency of peptides on perfluorosilane
326 nanostructured steel plates. However, the study did not describe the sensitivity or LOD values of peptides [1].

327 To quantify the beneficial effect of BDD modified interfaces for analysis of peptides, for every combination
328 of peptide-BDD interface LOD_{ratio} was calculated as $LOD_{ratio} = LOD_{steel} / LOD_{BDD}$. The higher LOD_{ratio} value the
329 better performance of peptide analysis by MALDI-MS on BDD interfaces in comparison to commercially
330 available ground steel chip. In **Tab. 4** we can identify especially three peptides, which showed significantly
331 enhanced LOD_{ratio} exceeding the value of 5 *i.e.* for *Sub P* peptide on continuous BDD with -H-termination
332 ($LOD_{ratio} = 7.03$), on continuous BDD with -O-termination ($LOD_{ratio} = 19.19$) and BDD nanotips surface with -H-
333 termination ($LOD_{ratio} = 5.42$) (**Tab. 4**). From all other peptide-BDD combinations, only two peptides could be
334 detected with significant LOD_{ratio} *i.e.* *Brad* on continuous BDD terminated by F- ($LOD_{ratio} = 5.92$) and *Ren S* on
335 BDD nanograss terminated by H- ($LOD_{ratio} = 14.94$) (**Tab. 4**).

336 To better understand why only those three peptides could be detected with such high LOD_{ratio} and on what
337 surface, additional analyses were performed. 3D plots showing the dependence of LOD_{ratio} on m/z and
338 charge of the peptides were prepared (**Fig. 8**). From these graphs it is clear that enhanced $LOD_{ratio} > 5.0$ was
339 observed for continuous BDD films terminated by all three terminations (-H, -O and -F; upper row in **Fig. 8**),
340 for BDD nanograss terminated by -H (middle image in the middle row in **Fig. 8**) and for BDD nanotips
341 terminated by -H (middle image in the lower row in **Fig. 8**). Let's correlate BDD samples revealing enhanced
342 LOD_{ratio} with electron affinity of their surfaces. Electron affinity of all BDD modified surfaces varies from +1.8
343 to -0.7 eV (**Tab. 3**). A closer inspection confirms that BDD surface termination which revealed enhanced
344 LOD_{ratio} exhibits moderate electron affinity values, *i.e.* -0.7 eV (continuous BDD, -H); -0.5 eV (BDD nanotips, -
345 H); -0.3 eV (BDD nanograss, -H), +0.8 eV (continuous BDD, -O) and +1.0 eV (continuous BDD, -F). If the
346 electron affinity exceeded the value of +1.4 eV, all LOD_{ratio} values were smaller than 5.0, indicating that there
347 might be an upper limit of electron affinity (*i.e.* ~ 1.0 – 1.4 eV), beyond which we could not observe $LOD_{ratio} > 5.0$
348 for any peptide used in the study. This might indicate that a moderate electron affinity of BDD samples, *i.e.*
349 electronegativity dipole drop at the surface, is beneficial for effective peptide analysis by MALDI-MS.

350 It is very important to also understand what features peptides need to have, to be detected on the BDD
351 surfaces with enhanced LOD_{ratio} values. **Tab. S1** indicates that the three peptides *Brad*, *Sub P* and *Ren S*
352 effectively detected on BDD interfaces by MALDI-MS exhibit a high percentage of hydrophobic amino acids
353 (54.5 - 57.2%) in combination with a low percentage of acidic amino acids (0 - 7.1%). Additional calculation
354 showed that such three amino acids *Brad*, *Sub P* and *Ren S* exhibit very low hydrophobicity values (10.03 -
355 14.50 kcal mol⁻¹). At the same time, these three amino acids *Brad*, *Sub P* and *Ren S* exhibit low charge at pH
356 7.4 (from -0.20 to +1.18) (**Tab. 1**). **Fig. S1** also shows the distribution of negative charge, positive charge,
357 and hydrophobic patches on the surface of peptides. So, we can assume that especially amino acids with
358 high hydrophobicity and low charge density are effectively detected by MALDI-MS.

359 We can conclude that the reason why especially *Brad*, *Sub P* and *Ren S* were effectively detected on
360 some BDD samples is the hydrophobic interaction between the BDD surface (represented by electron affinity
361 values *i.e.* from -0.3 eV to +1.0 eV) and hydrophobic peptides.

362 It is also important to understand the optimal surface termination and morphology of the BDD for MALDI-
363 MS analysis of highly hydrophilic (highly acidic or highly basic) peptides. The results demonstrate that for
364 highly acidic AC18 peptide (*i.e.* negatively charged with a charge at pH 7.4 of -3.82; pI of 4.3) (**Tab. 1** and
365 **Fig. S1**) the highest $LOD_{ratio}=4.21$ was obtained on hydrophilic continuous BDD terminated with -O (electron
366 affinity of +0.8 eV, negative electronegativity potential drop). Highly basic AC1 peptide (*i.e.* positively charged
367 with the charge at pH 7.4 of +3.26; pI of 10.3) (**Tab. 1** and **Fig. S1**) the highest $LOD_{ratio}=2.78$ was obtained on
368 hydrophobic continuous BDD terminated with -H (electron affinity of -0.7 eV, positive electronegativity
369 potential drop) (**Fig. 10**). Thus, we can conclude that highly acidic and basic peptides can be detected on
370 BDD surfaces having the opposite wetting properties, *i.e.* interfacial charge and electron affinity.

371 Analysis of peptides on BDD surfaces could be affected also by other parameters of the interface such as
372 the work function (WF) (**Tab. 3**) of the BDD interfaces. The dependence between LOD_{ratio} and WF for *Sub P*
373 peptide shows a linear decrease of LOD_{ratio} with WF with one exception (shown in red circle in **Fig. 9**).

374 Thus, it seems that the value of EA of the BDD interfaces might be an important factor for the effective
375 adsorption of peptides on BDD interfaces *via* hydrophobic interactions (*Ren S*, *Brad* and *Sub P*) or *via*
376 electrostatic interactions (*AC1* and *AC18*). There are of course other types of interactions, which might be
377 important for adsorption of peptides on BDD interfaces *i.e.* hydrogen bond interactions. The other factor
378 which can contribute towards the effectiveness of peptide analysis, might be WF of the BDD interfaces. It was
379 already postulated that the main role of the matrix applied for MALDI-MS assays is to affect the work function
380 of the metallic interface resulting in a change of the electronic structure of the organic-metal interface
381 affecting both the kinetic energy and the flux of released electrons [38, 39]. The results shown here are only
382 preliminary revealing key factors behind effective peptide analysis on BDD using MALDI-TOF MS. Further
383 investigation is still needed to better understand a complex interplay of interfacial factors of BDD and physico-
384 chemical properties of peptides behind peptide analysis on BDD using MALDI-TOF MS.

385 It is important to highlight that some of the peptides could be detected using MALDI-TOF MS on BDD in
386 an very sensitive fashion with LOD as low as 2.3 pM, what is a prerequisite for diagnostics of several
387 diseases at early stages

388
389 **Figure 9:** The influence of work function (WF) on LOD_{ratio} values for *Sub P* peptide. The data point marked by red circle
390 was not part of the linear plot.
391

392 Conclusions

393 Our study has demonstrated, for the first time, the effective application of BDD chips for the detection of 9
394 representative peptides using MALDI-MS. The two critical parameters for the effective detection of peptides
395 on nanostructured BDD surfaces were identified: type of atomic termination of BDD surface and
396 hydrophobicity of peptides. We found that BDD surfaces allowed us to effectively detect hydrophobic amino
397 acids on moderately processed BDD nanostructured interfaces. At the same time, we observed that positively
398 charged peptides could be detected on hydrophobic BDD surfaces and negatively charged peptides on
399 hydrophilic BDD surfaces. Based on these findings, we can conclude that to achieve effective detection of
400 peptides, it is necessary to tailor the BDD interface with high affinity towards the target peptides. This means
401 utilizing hydrophobic interactions for hydrophobic peptides and electrostatic interactions for charged peptides.
402 In future research, we intend to explore whether other biomolecules besides peptides can be effectively
403 detected on BDD surfaces by MALDI-MS. Furthermore, we aim to determine the optimal interfacial properties
404 (top surface morphology, conductivity, wetting properties, electron affinity, etc.) of BDD surfaces for such
405 assays. Overall, our findings highlight the potential of BDD chips as a tailorable material platform for peptide
406 detection and pave the way for further advancements in this field. Further work is however necessary to
407 understand a complex interplay of the interfacial BDD interfaces on peptide adsorption and on the ability of
408 such interfaces to release electrons for ionisation of the analyte molecules.

409

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